

Illustrated Story Book Media to Improve Reading Skills in Indonesian Language Learning for Second Grade of Elementary School Students

Kadek Dwi Nanditasari^{1*}, I Made Citra Wibawa²

^{1,2} Pendidikan Guru Sekolah Dasar, Universitas Pendidikan Ganesha, Singaraja, Indonesia

ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received February 08, 2024

Accepted June 10, 2024

Available online July 25, 2024

Kata Kunci:

Media Pembelajaran, Buku Cerita Bergambar, Kemampuan Membaca

Keywords:

Learning Media, Illustrated Story Book, Reading Skills

This is an open access article under the CC BY-SA license.

Copyright © 2024 by Author. Published by Universitas Pendidikan Ganesha.

ABSTRAK

Kemampuan siswa dalam membaca masih rendah. Hal tersebut dikarenakan tidak tersedianya media pendukung interaktif, yang ada hanya berupa buku yang didominasi banyak tulisan. Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk membuktikan efektivitas media buku cerita bergambar pada pembelajaran bahasa Indonesia untuk meningkatkan kemampuan membaca siswa kelas II SD. Jenis penelitian ini adalah pengembangan. Model yang digunakan yaitu ADDIE yang terdiri dari lima tahapan, yaitu analisis (analyze), perancangan (design), pengembangan (development), implementasi (implementation), dan evaluasi (evaluation). Subjek pada penelitian ini adalah siswa kelas II sebanyak 17 siswa. Metode pengumpulan data menggunakan angket dan evaluasi kemampuan membaca lisan. Instrumen yang digunakan yakni angket dan tes. Teknik analisis data yang digunakan yaitu analisis deskriptif kualitatif, kuantitatif, dan statistik inferensial. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan nilai signifikansi (2-tailed) sebesar 0,000 pada uji-t sehingga disimpulkan bahwa media buku cerita bergambar untuk meningkatkan kemampuan membaca pada pembelajaran bahasa Indonesia siswa kelas II layak digunakan sebagai media pembelajaran dalam proses pembelajaran. Implikasi penelitian ini yakni mampu menjadi contoh bagi guru dalam menggunakan media interaktif dalam pembelajaran untuk meningkatkan kemampuan membaca siswa.

ABSTRACT

Students' ability to read is still low. This is because there is no interactive supporting media available, only books which are dominated by lots of writing. This research aims to prove the effectiveness of picture story book media in Indonesian language learning to improve the reading ability of second grade elementary school students. This type of research is development. The model used is ADDIE which consists of five stages, namely analysis, design, development, implementation and evaluation. The subjects in this research were 17 class II students. The data collection method uses a questionnaire and evaluates oral reading ability. The instruments used were questionnaires and tests. The data analysis techniques used are qualitative descriptive analysis, quantitative and inferential statistics. The results of the research show a significance value (2-tailed) of 0.000 in the t-test so that it is concluded that the picture story book media for improving reading skills in class II students' Indonesian language learning is suitable for use as a learning medium in the learning process. The implication of this research is that it can be an example for teachers in using interactive media in learning to improve students' reading skills.

1. INTRODUCTION

Reading is not only an activity of recognizing letters and words, but also a window into knowledge, understanding, and critical thinking skills. Mastering reading skills at an early level of education is an important step in preparing individuals to achieve academic success and contribute to the wider order of society. However, in reality, elementary school students still have difficulty in reading skills. This is due to many factors, such as the lack of media that can attract students' interest in learning to read. Moreover, lower grade students still enjoy playing. Achieving learning objectives involves understanding various components of learning, including media, learning resources, materials, methods, evaluations, students, and teachers. The use of interesting learning media is one way to help in implementing a good learning process. The use of well-designed and creative learning media can improve student learning outcomes, improve

understanding of the material, and improve students' abilities in carrying out specific skills that are in accordance with learning objectives. However, currently the use of learning media is still lacking, this is related to reading skills (Boentolo et al., 2024; Maritsa et al., 2021).

Based on observation activities conducted at SD Negeri 3 Pakisan, there has been no utilization of media variations during learning, especially during Indonesian language lessons. Learning activities are still dominated by the delivery of information. There are situations where teachers have not been optimal in utilizing interactive media, even in some learning activities, there is no interactive supporting media available to support learning, especially reading (Hanikah et al., 2022; Putu et al., 2022). The books provided to support learning activities are dominated by a lot of writing. Then, through the results of interviews with the homeroom teacher of class II of SD Negeri 3 Pakisan, it was shown that out of 17 students, only 4 students could be categorized as very good in pronouncing letters/words and reading fluently without help from the teacher. The rest are included in low reading ability. When reading, students still spell and stutter, there are some who still make mistakes in pronouncing letters and words, are not precise in emphasizing the high and low tones when reading so that they still need help from the teacher when reading. One of the main factors causing this is that the use of media is still not varied during Indonesian language lessons (Amelia et al., 2022; Dwiqi et al., 2020). Because teachers still apply the lecture method in delivering material, so that learning still takes place in one direction. Learning that is more focused on teachers who only rely on the teacher's speaking ability in explaining, without utilizing learning media, can result in lack of enthusiasm and boredom in students when following the learning process (Apriliani & Radia, 2020; Agustina & Koeswanti, 2022).

It is known that students have low reading skills. Not only that, based on a survey conducted by the Programme For International Student Assessment (PISA) it shows that for the past three years, Indonesia has been ranked 64th out of 72 countries in the reading ability category in 2015. Then in 2018 Indonesia experienced a decline in ranking from the previous ranking of 64 in 2018 to 74 in 2018 but with a reading score that decreased from 397 in 2015 to 371 in 2018. Continuing in 2022, Indonesia rose 9 positions, from previously ranked 74 in 2018 to 63 in 2022 while still experiencing a decline in scores from 371 in 2018 to 366 in 2022. Based on the results of the PISA survey, students' reading ability is still at a low level compared to other countries. This is a concern that must be focused on students' reading skills because in an increasingly advanced society, reading skills are a necessity, because some information is presented in writing and can only be obtained through reading activities, even visual information via television also requires reading skills (Septianti & Afiani, 2020).

Most of the books that are available do not have pictures and if there are any pictures, the pictures are not colored so they are very abstract for students. Students feel bored because the books contain a lot of text that dominates (Septianti & Afiani, 2020; (2019)). Learning that is less interesting and less interactive due to the absence of appropriate media or lack of media utilization has caused reading to become an activity that is carried out mechanically and is less interesting for students. Thus, the inability to integrate appropriate and interactive media in the learning process has contributed to the low reading ability of students. This underlines the urgency to make improvements in learning methods and the development of learning tools that are more interactive and in accordance with student needs. Therefore, interesting media is needed to increase students' interest in reading and also media that can help them find information while reading, as well as increase students' reading motivation (Swihadayani, 2023). Students in the lower grades of elementary school tend to be more interested in interactive and fun learning experiences. This is because the cognitive level of elementary school students is still at the concrete operational level, which means they need concrete or semi-concrete media to describe or visualize something. They have a special attraction to images that bring learning materials to life. So it will be easier for students in the lower grades who are generally just starting to read by providing reading materials that have lots of images (Swihadayani, 2023; Ali, 2022).

The role of images in student reading books not only attracts students' interest, but also acts as a concrete object to help them think. The increase in reading ability is in line with picture story books, story books shown to children place the student's point of view in it as the center, so that students can choose picture story books with the student's glasses, in addition, picture story books can improve students' reading ability (Ali & Asrial, 2022; Ulfah Mawaddah et al., 2023). Picture story books are useful in helping students describe the plot and content of the story more easily, as well as making the story more unique and interesting (Agustina & Koeswanti, 2022; (Helsa & Kenedi, 2019)). Several studies have shown that picture books can improve students' reading skills. Picture story media greatly influences students' reading development results. Thus, picture books are expected to be able to improve students' reading skills. This study is novel because it presents books with many interesting and colorful pictures so that students are interested in reading books. Different from books on the market that only contain writing.

The teacher expressed his agreement on the development of picture story book media for grade II elementary school students. In order to help students, improve their reading skills, picture story books will

be made attractive in terms of covers, designs, pictures, and stories that emphasize a material in learning Indonesian. Based on this explanation, a development study was conducted to prove the effectiveness of picture story book media to improve reading skills in learning Indonesian for grade II students. By conducting this study, it is hoped that it can be a reference for teachers in providing Indonesian language learning, especially reading skills for grade II students in elementary schools (Apriliani & Radia, 2020; Paramita et al., 2022).

2. METHOD

This type of research is development research. The model used as a guideline in product development is the ADDIE model which consists of the analysis stage (Analyze) the implementation of the analysis stage in this development research begins by carrying out 3 steps including needs analysis (Kamiana et al., 2019; Mahardika et al., 2023), characteristic analysis and curriculum analysis. Then, the design stage of learning media starts from compiling a story script (storyline), making a design draft for a picture story book media which is then consulted with the supervisor to be given input and suggestions, then continued to the media creation stage. The development stage is carried out by judges testing to determine the validity of the research instrument, the realization of real media from what has been made in the design stage into a product, and media validation testing by experts. Expert testing activities are carried out by 2 experts. The implementation stage is carried out if the results of the expert test have met the criteria (good). The activities carried out are trying out or implementing media in the field to determine its effect on the quality of learning, and evaluation is carried out after the use of picture story book learning media on fable stories. This evaluation aims to assess the impact of media on improving students' reading skills during the learning process. Product trials at the implementation stage use the pre-experimental method with the One Group Pretest-Posttest Design. The subjects of this study were 17 second grade students

The data collection methods used to obtain data and information in this study were questionnaires and reading ability evaluations. The questionnaire used in this study was a validity and effectiveness questionnaire that aimed to collect data from reviews by material experts and learning media experts, teachers, and students. In addition, to determine the effectiveness of using picture story book media, students were then given an oral reading ability evaluation from the total number of class II students. The instruments used to collect data in this development research were questionnaires and oral reading ability tests. The questionnaire was a list of written questions that had to be answered by respondents, and the questionnaire used in this study was a closed questionnaire, meaning that the questionnaire had already provided answers so that respondents only had to choose the existing answers. The instrument grid for media experts is presented in Table 1, the grid for material experts in Table 2, the grid for practitioners in Table 3, the grid for students in Table 4 and the grid for effectiveness tests in Table 5.

Table 1. The Media Expert Picture Story Book Media Instrument Grid

No.	Aspect	Indicator
1	Graphic Eligibility	a. Book size b. Cover design c. Layout d. Color e. Font size f. Font selection g. Clarity of image illustration h. Placement of image illustrations i. Balance of shape, color and size of the image j. Clarity of image captions (captions) k. Placement of titles, subtitles, and image captions

Table 2. The Grid of Picture Story Book Media Instruments for Material Experts

No.	Aspect	Indicator
1	Content/Material Suitability	a. Completeness of materials b. Breadth of material c. Depth of material d. Relevance of the material e. Accuracy of images and illustrations f. Accuracy of terms

No.	Aspect	Indicator
2	Presentation	g Consistency of systematic presentation of material
		h Conceptual breakdown
		i Introduction
		j Glossary
		k Summary
3	Language Eligibility	l Interactivity
		m Compliance with the intellectual development of students
		n Compliance with the emotional development of students
		o Correctness of sentence structure
		p Effectiveness of sentences
		q Spelling accuracy
		r Grammatical correctness
		s Standardization of terms

Table 3. The Grid of Picture Story Book Media Instruments for Practitioners

No.	Aspect	Indicator
1	Appearance	a. Book cover design
		b. Clarity of image illustration
		c. Caption
		d. The attraction of color
2	Material	a. Completeness of materials
		b. Breadth of material
		c. Depth of material
		d. Relevance of the material
3	Typography	a. The appeal of using text variations
		b. Text size accuracy
4	Presentation	a. Consistency of systematic presentation of material
		b. Interactivity
5	Language	a. Accuracy of language style
		b. Spelling accuracy
		c. Effectiveness of sentences

Table 4. The Grid of Media Instruments for Picture Story Books for Students

No.	Aspect	Indicator
1	Appearance	a. Book size
		b. Book cover design
		c. Images and illustrations
2	Material	a. Compliance with the subject matter
		b. Completeness of story content
		c. Level of understanding of story content
3	Presentation	a. Systematic presentation of material in story books
		b. Story summary
		c. Explanation of difficult terms or vocabulary
		d. Interactivity
4	Typography	a. Text size accuracy
		b. Text type variations
		c. The attractiveness of text color
5	Language	a. Level of ease of language style

Table 5. The Grid of Student Reading Ability Assessment Instrument

No.	Elements to be Assessed
1	Pronunciation
2	Intonation
3	Smoothness
4	Clarity of voice

The data analysis method used in this study is qualitative and quantitative data analysis. Qualitative data analysis is carried out using descriptive techniques, namely data processing in the form of descriptions, statements, input, and suggestions that will be analyzed first and then presented with descriptions in the form of new sentences or descriptions (Andriyani & Suniasih, 2021; Dewi & Negara, 2021). Quantitative data analysis techniques are carried out when presenting the results of the media feasibility test based on the results of the questionnaire that has been given to the validator and trial subjects. Analysis of the effectiveness of the media on students' reading ability is carried out using the paired t-test formula through the SPSS program.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

This research went through five stages according to the ADDIE development model, namely analysis, design, development, implementation, and evaluation. The activities that have been carried out by researchers at each stage of development are. The first stage is analysis, before the picture story book media is developed, the analysis stage is carried out with the aim of obtaining product development needs such as problems faced by students and teachers, availability of learning materials or media, competencies achieved by students, analysis of student characteristics, and collection of information about the media needed by students and teachers in the learning process (Fitria et al., 2020; Nuraini et al., 2020). Related to the availability of learning media in the classroom, information was obtained that the books provided to support learning activities are dominated by a lot of writing. Especially in Indonesian language lessons, the use of media is still not varied because only books are available that are dominated by a lot of writing so that students are bored because learning takes place in one direction, namely focusing on teachers who rely on the teacher's speaking ability when explaining (lecture method in delivering material). Based on this, the development of media to help support learning activities so that students do not get bored and lazy when reading books is needed to improve their reading skills. The results of the analysis also revealed that students' habits prefer to look at pictures without paying attention to the correct vocabulary when reading. Therefore, the development of illustrated story book media in Indonesian language learning to improve the reading skills of grade II students of SD Negeri 3 Pakisan.

The second stage, namely the design stage, is designed referring to the results of the analysis that has been carried out previously. The design of the illustrated story book media begins with compiling a storyline through Microsoft Word 2019 and a media framework before being developed. Then continued with the third stage, namely the development stage. At the development stage, the creation of the developed media begins. The developed media consists of character figures, covers, forewords, learning objectives, character introductions, contents, summaries, conclusions, new vocabulary accompanied by definitions, author information, and a back-cover synopsis. The appearance of the media that has been created can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The Display of Illustrated Story Book Media

The developed picture story book media was then tested by learning material experts, learning media experts, and practitioners. The assessment was carried out by filling out the product validation sheet. The assessment given by the experts was carried out to determine the level of validity of the development of picture story book media. The results of the assessment given by the experts were the average percentage obtained by the material experts, namely 98%, so they were in a very good qualification. The average percentage obtained by the material experts was 98%, so they were in a very good qualification. The average percentage obtained by the practitioners was 98%, so they were in a very good qualification.

The fourth stage is implementation, at the implementation stage, the media is implemented in the field after going through testing and revision. The implementation of the media aims to measure how realistic the learning media is used to support the learning process by students. Then, the media will also be assessed by students through a questionnaire. The results of the assessment given by 9 students of grade II of SD Negeri 3 Pakisan. The average percentage obtained from student responses was 98.46% and was included in the range of 85-100% so that it can be said that the results of the media practicality assessment were in a very good qualification. There was no input and suggestions given by students regarding the illustrated story book media.

The evaluation stage was carried out at each stage flow to improve the quality of the development of fable picture story book media in Indonesian language learning to improve the reading ability of class II students of SD Negeri 3 Pakisan. In addition, at the evaluation stage, an effectiveness test of picture story book learning media was also carried out to determine the effect of picture story book media on improving the reading ability of class II students of SD Negeri 3 Pakisan. The effectiveness test was carried out using SPSS version 25. However, before conducting the effectiveness test, a normality prerequisite test and a homogeneity prerequisite test were carried out first. Based on the results of the data analysis, the significance value for Shapiro-Wilk on the reading ability value before media implementation (pre-test) was 0.087. These results indicate that the significance value of 0.087 is greater than 0.05 so it can be concluded that the reading ability value before media implementation (pre-test) is normally distributed. Then the reading ability value after media implementation (post-test) obtained a significance value of 0.142. The results show that the significance value of 0.142 is greater than 0.05 so it can be concluded that the reading ability scores after media implementation (post-test) are normally distributed. The results of the t-test using SPSS can be seen in Table 6.

Table 6. Normality Test Results

Variable/Data Group	Kolmogorov-Smirnova			Shapiro Wilk		
	Statistics	df	Sig.	Statistics	df	Sig.
Pre-test	0.158	17	0.200	0.906	17	0.087
Post-test	0.181	17	0.144	0.919	17	0.142

Then, based on the results of the data analysis of the homogeneity of variance test, the significance value in the Based on Mean column obtained a value of 0.175. These results indicate that the significance value of 0.175 is greater than 0.05 so that the reading ability value before media implementation (pre-test) and the reading ability value after media implementation (post-test) are declared homogeneous. The results of the homogeneity test can be seen in Table 7.

Table 7. Homogeneity Test Results

Parameters	Levene Statistics		df1	df2	Sig.
	Based on Mean	Based on Median			
Based on Mean	1.926	1	32	0.175	
Based on Median	1.719	1	32	0.199	
Based on Median and with adjusted df	1.719	1	31.160	0.199	
Based on trimmed mean	1.867	1	32	0.181	

After the prerequisite test was conducted, then an effectiveness test was conducted using the t-test. Based on the results of the data analysis, it was found that the significance value (2-tailed) was 0.000. These results indicate that the significance value is less than 0.05. Based on these results, H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted so that it can be concluded that there is a significant difference in the reading ability of grade II students before learning using picture story book media and after learning using picture story book media. The results of the t-test can be seen in Table 8.

Table 8. Results of Effectiveness Test

Paired Group	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 Pretest-Posttest	-5.765	1.715	0.416	-6.646	-4.883	-13.859	16	0.000

By presenting the material consistently into a story accompanied by clear punctuation, it helps students to regulate the pitch and sentence structure. The overall typography makes it easier for students to identify letters and words more quickly and accurately, which in turn supports correct pronunciation and the development of more effective reading skills. Accompanied by the appropriateness of simple language (found every day) and in accordance with the level of intellectual development of students, it helps students pronounce words correctly and supports students' reading fluency which ultimately effectively improves students' reading skills.

Discussion

The development of picture story book media has very good qualifications because in its preparation it uses the ADDIE model which has a systematic flow. Other studies conducted state that learning media products have very good qualifications if they use a systematic model. Other research findings also reveal that the ADDIE model is very good for use in developing a media product. The feasibility of picture story book media can also be seen from the suitability of the characteristics of elementary school students who are at the concrete operational stage (Amelia et al., 2022; Septianti & Afiani, 2020). At this stage, children need help from real objects in their learning process. The cognitive development of children is explained in that at the concrete operational stage (7-12 years), children are mature enough to use logical thinking or operations, but only for physical objects that currently exist (Juwantara, 2019; Tristanti & Wisdom, 2021). Picture story books have an attraction that is expected to stimulate students to think concretely and develop their logical abilities, because the pictures in the story books can be clearly seen by students.

The suitability of the developed picture story book media meets the media development aspects seen from its content which integrates material into a story form. In terms of learning content, the elements achieved, the suitability of basic competencies, and learning objectives presented in the media make it easier for students to understand the material taught by the teacher (Gulo & Harefa, 2022; Rahmawati & Atmojo, 2021). The suitability of learning media with learning objectives makes it easier for students to learn. The relevance of the material in picture story book media also helps students understand the material more easily because it is delivered sequentially and clearly, making it easier for students to absorb information in the reading. Supported by other researchers who state that the clarity of the media will make it easier for students to understand the learning material (K. Mertami et al., 2023). The interactivity in the process of integrating material into the story also adds a plus point to the illustrated storybook media through narration that invites students to read, remember, and ask questions.

Picture story book media has met the requirements as a learning media that is suitable for use in learning. This can be seen from the suitability and clarity of the images presented with the material contained therein (Apriliani & Radia, 2020; Tristanti & Hikmat, 2021). Other studies state that the suitability of images greatly determines the success of learning media in presenting information. Images in picture books can trigger students' emotional involvement in the story and its characters. This makes learning more interesting and motivates students to read and learn further. When compared to books that are only dominated by lots of text, it will make students bored and have no interest in reading the book. Students feel bored because the book contains a lot of text that dominates. Other findings state that interesting picture media will attract children's attention and provide an initial response to the learning process. The availability of picture books that combine narrative text with supporting images can stimulate students' imaginations to express attitudes and reactions based on the development of the story presented (K. Mertami et al., 2023; KMA Dwiyasari et al., 2023).

Picture story book media can be used by students to read anytime and anywhere because the form is provided in concrete and digital form. The suitability of picture story book media with student characteristics and learning materials becomes the attraction for students in learning. This is because the picture story book images combine the use of text and images, thus involving more of the students' senses (sight, hearing, and touch) in the learning process. Interesting and colorful picture story books and accompanied by the use of letter variations in the story text can increase students' motivation to read. The availability of picture story books that combine narrative text with supporting images can stimulate students' imagination to express attitudes and reactions based on the development of the story presented (Mertami et al., 2023; (Septianti & Afiani, 2020).

Although this research has been conducted and the research objectives have been met, there are still limitations in this research. These limitations include the development of picture story books based on the problem of reading ability of grade II students at SD Negeri 3 Pakisan. The picture story books made are only limited to 1 fable story entitled "Ingenuity Brings Goodness". It is hoped that in further research, research can be conducted with a broader problem analysis in other schools and more material.

The implication of this development research is that illustrated storybook media in Indonesian language learning can improve the reading skills of grade II elementary school students with very good

predicates or qualifications (Agustina & Koeswanti, 2022; Tanjung et al., 2021). Picture story book media is used as a tool to support the learning process, especially in improving students' reading skills. For an effective learning process, teachers must be able to understand the characteristics of the students being taught and the students' learning needs. In theory, students in grade II of elementary school are at the concrete operational stage where students have begun to think and need concrete objects to help in their learning process. The existence of picture story book media helps teachers and students in the learning process, making it easier for teachers to improve students' reading skills so that optimal learning is created (Juliantari, 2017; Nurmahanani & Mulyati, 2022).

The advantages of this study are the suitability with the characteristics of students at the concrete operational stage, the visual appeal that can motivate students, and the ability of the book to facilitate students in understanding the learning material. This book also allows the integration of interactivity in learning, thereby increasing students' emotional and cognitive involvement.

4. CONCLUSION

The conclusion of this study shows that the illustrated storybook media developed using the ADDIE model has successfully obtained very good qualifications as a learning aid. This book meets the needs of second grade elementary school students who are at the concrete operational stage, where they need visual aids to support the logical thinking process. The use of relevant images and interesting narratives can increase student motivation and involvement in learning. This media is also effective in helping students understand learning materials more easily and improving their reading skills. Although this study is limited to one fable story, these findings provide a strong basis for the development of similar media with a wider scope in the future, as well as the integration of more diverse materials to support more optimal learning.

5. REFERENCE

- Agustina, R. C., & Koeswanti, H. D. (2022). Pengembangan Media Pembelajaran Bucergam untuk Meningkatkan Kemampuan Membaca Siswa Kelas I SD. *Jurnal Basicedu*, 6(5), 8736–8745. <https://doi.org/10.31004/basicedu.v6i5.3935>.
- Ali, M., & Asrial, A. (2022). Peningkatan Kemampuan Membaca Peserta Didik Kelas II SDN 136/I Semangkat Melalui Buku Cerita Bergambar. *Jurnal Tonggak Pendidikan Dasar : Jurnal Kajian Teori Dan Hasil Pendidikan Dasar*, 1(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.22437/jtpd.v1i1.19406>.
- Amelia, S., Wedi, A., & Husna, A. (2022). PENGEMBANGAN MODUL BERBANTUAN TEKNOLOGI AUGMENTED REALITY DENGAN PUZZLE PADA MATERI BANGUN RUANG. *JKTP: Jurnal Kajian Teknologi Pendidikan*, 5(1), 62–71. <https://doi.org/10.17977/um038v5i12022p062>.
- Andriyani, N. L., & Suniasih, N. W. (2021). Development of Learning Videos Based on Problem-Solving Characteristics of Animals and Their Habitats Contain in Ipa Subjects on 6th-Grade. *Journal of Education Technology*, 1(1), 37–47. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.23887/jet.v5i1.32314>.
- Apriliani, S. P., & Radia, E. H. (2020). Pengembangan Media Pembelajaran Buku Cerita Bergambar Untuk Meningkatkan Minat Membaca Siswa Sekolah Dasar. *Jurnal Basicedu*, 4(4), 994–1003. <https://doi.org/10.31004/basicedu.v4i4.492>.
- Boentolo, F., Manu, C.-C. C. R., Saragih, O. G., & Zalukhu, S. (2024). Peran Guru Memanfaatkan AI dalam Membangun Generasi Unggul Menuju Indonesia Emas 2045. *Aletheia Christian Educators Journal*, 5(1), 42–48. <https://doi.org/10.9744/aletheia.5.1.42-48>.
- Dewi, N. M. L. C., & Negara, I. G. A. O. (2021). Pengembangan Media Video Animasi IPA pada Pokok Bahasan Sistem Pernapasan Kelas V. *Jurnal Edutech Undiksha*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.23887/jeu.v9i1.32501>
- Dwiqui, G. C. S., Sudatha, I. G. W., & Sukmana, A. I. W. I. Y. (2020). Implementation of Tri-N (Niteni-Nirokke-Nambahi) and PPK (Strengthening of Character Education) in Explanation Text Learning Development of Grade 8th. *Proceedings: The International Conference on Technology, Education, and Science*, 1(1), 33.
- Fitria, R., Suparman, Hairun, Y., & Ruhama, M. A. H. (2020). Student's worksheet design for social arithmetic based on PBL to increase the critical thinking skills. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 8(5), 2028–2046. <https://doi.org/10.13189/ujer.2020.080541>.
- Gulo, S., & Harefa, A. O. (2022). Pengembangan Media Pembelajaran Interaktif Berbasis Powerpoint. *Educativo: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 1(1), 291–299. <https://doi.org/10.56248/educativo.v1i1.40>.
- Hanikah, H., Faiz, A., Nurhabibah, P., & Wardani, M. A. (2022). Penggunaan Media Interaktif Berbasis Ebook di Sekolah Dasar. *Jurnal Basicedu*, 6(4), 7352–7359. <https://doi.org/10.31004/basicedu.v6i4.3503>.
- Helsa, Y., & Kenedi, A. K. (2019). Edmodo-Based Blended Learning Media in Learning Mathematics. *JOURNAL OF TEACHING AND LEARNING IN ELEMENTARY EDUCATION (JTLEE)*, 2(2), 107–117.

- <https://doi.org/10.33578/jtlee.v2i2.7416>.
- Juliantari, N. K. (2017). Paradigma Analisis Wacana Dalam Memahami Teks Dan Konteks Untuk Meningkatkan Kemampuan Membaca Pemahaman. *Acarya Pustaka*, 3(1), 12. <https://doi.org/10.23887/ap.v3i1.12732>.
- Juwantara, R. A. (2019). Analisis Teori Perkembangan Kognitif Piaget pada Tahap Anak Usia Operasional Konkret 7-12 Tahun dalam Pembelajaran Matematika. *Al-Adzka: Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan Guru Madrasah Ibtidaiyah*, 9(1), 27. <https://doi.org/10.18592/aladzkapgmi.v9i1.3011>.
- K. Mertami, I.G. Margunayasa, & I.B.P. Arnyana. (2023). Pengembangan Buku Cerita Bergambar Bermuatan Pendidikan Karakter Sebagai Sarana Literasi Membaca Untuk Siswa. *PENDASI: Jurnal Pendidikan Dasar Indonesia*, 7(1), 83–93. https://doi.org/10.23887/jurnal_pendas.v7i1.2041.
- K.M.A. Dwiyasari, I.B.P. Arnyana, & I.G. Astawan. (2023). Pengembangan Buku Cerita Bergambar Bermuatan Pendidikan Karakter Untuk Meningkatkan Kemampuan Membaca Pada Siswa Kelas Ii Sd. *PENDASI: Jurnal Pendidikan Dasar Indonesia*, 7(1), 71–82. https://doi.org/10.23887/jurnal_pendas.v7i1.2023.
- Kamiana, A., Kesiman, M. W. A., & Pradnyana, G. A. (2019). Pengembangan Augmented Reality Book Sebagai Media Pembelajaran Virus Berbasis Android. *Kumpulan Artikel Mahasiswa Pendidikan Teknik Informatika (KARMAPATI)*, 8(2), 165. <https://doi.org/10.23887/karmapati.v8i2.18351>.
- Mahardika, E. K., Nurmanita, T. S., Anam, K., & Prasetyo, M. A. (2023). Strategi Literasi Budaya Anak Usia Dini melalui Pengembangan Game Edukatif. *Murhum : Jurnal Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini*, 4(2), 80–93. <https://doi.org/10.37985/murhum.v4i2.287>.
- Maritsa, A., Hanifah Salsabila, U., Wafiq, M., Rahma Anindya, P., & Azhar Ma'shum, M. (2021). Pengaruh Teknologi Dalam Dunia Pendidikan. *Al-Mutharahah: Jurnal Penelitian Dan Kajian Sosial Keagamaan*, 18(2), 91–100. <https://doi.org/10.46781/al-mutharahah.v18i2.303>.
- Nuraini, I., Sutama, S., & Narimo, S. (2020). Pengembangan Media Pembelajaran Berbasis PowerPoint iSpring Suite 8 di Sekolah Dasar. *Jurnal VARIDIKA*, 31(2), 62–71. <https://doi.org/10.23917/varidika.v31i2.10220>.
- Nurmahanani, I., & Mulyati, Y. (2022). Penerapan Model Sosiokognitif Berbantuan Multimedia Interaktif dalam Pembelajaran Menulis Teks Deskripsi di Sekolah Dasar. *Jurnal Basicedu*, 6(6), 9432–9439. <https://doi.org/10.31004/basicedu.v6i6.4080>.
- Paramita, G. A. P. P., Gede Agung, A. A., & Abadi, I. B. G. S. (2022). Buku Cerita Bergambar Guna Meningkatkan Keterampilan Membaca Muatan Pelajaran Bahasa Indonesia Siswa Kelas III SD. *Mimbar Ilmu*, 27(1), 11–19. <https://doi.org/10.23887/mi.v27i1.45499>.
- Putra, I. P. S., Suastra, I. W., & Suarni, N. K. (2021). Program Studi Pendidikan Dasar Universitas Pendidikan Ganesha. *PENDASI: Jurnal Pendidikan Dasar Indonesia*, 5(2), 203–213. https://ejournal2.undiksha.ac.id/index.php/jurnal_pendas/article/view/290/332.
- Putri, N. (2019). Buku Cerita Fabel Berbasis Pendidikan Karakter Untuk Siswa Sekolah Dasar Kelas Tinggi. *Jurnal Lentera Pendidikan Pusat Penelitian LPPM UM METRO*, 4(2), 126–143.
- Putu, N., Wirantini, N., Astawan, G., & Gede Margunayasa, I. (2022). Media Pembelajaran berbasis Multimedia Interaktif pada Topik Siklus Air. *Jurnal Edutech Undiksha*, 10(1), 42–51. <https://doi.org/10.23887/jeu.v10i1.46558>.
- Rahmawati, F., & Atmojo, I. R. W. (2021). Analisis Media Digital Video Pembelajaran Abad 21 Menggunakan Aplikasi Canva Pada Pembelajaran IPA. *Jurnal Basicedu*, 5(6), 6271–6279. <https://doi.org/10.31004/basicedu.v5i6.1717>.
- Septianti, N., & Afiani, R. (2020). Pentingnya Memahami Karakteristik Siswa Sekolah Dasar di SDN Cikokol 2. *AS-SABIQUN*, 2(1), 7–17. <https://doi.org/10.36088/assabiqun.v2i1.611>.
- Swihadayani, N. (2023). Karakteristik Siswa Kelas Rendah Sekolah Dasar. *Jurnal Sosial Teknologi*, 3(6), 488–493. <https://doi.org/10.59188/jurnalsostech.v3i6.810>.
- Tanjung, R., Supandi, & Moch Toyyib, A. (2021). Penerapan Metode Scramble Dalam Meningkatkan Kemampuan Membaca Pemahaman Siswa Pada Pembelajaran Bahasa Indonesia Di Kelas V Sd Negeri Pasirkaliki Ii Karawang. *Jurnal Tahsinia*, 2(2), 124–133. <https://doi.org/10.57171/jt.v2i2.299>.
- Trisanti, Z. A., & Hikmat, A. (2021). Pengembangan Media Buku Cerita Bergambar terhadap Minat Membaca Siswa pada Mata Pelajaran Bahasa Indonesia. *Jurnal Basicedu*, 5(6), 6017–6024. <https://doi.org/10.31004/basicedu.v5i6.1829>.
- Ulfah Mawaddah, F., Safrina, R., & Hapidin, H. (2023). Buku Cerita Bergambar Digital “Baso dan Pinisi yang Rusak” untuk Meningkatkan Literasi Budaya Maritim Anak. *Murhum : Jurnal Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini*, 4(2), 222–237. <https://doi.org/10.37985/murhum.v4i2.312>.
- Yayan Alpian, Sri Wulan Anggraeni, Unika Wiharti, & Nizmah Maratos Soleha. (2019). Pentingnya Pendidikan Bagi Manusia. *JURNAL BUANA PENGABDIAN*, 1(1), 66–72. <https://doi.org/10.36805/jurnalbuanapengabdian.v1i1.581>.